

Complex Chromium Ammonium Compounds

BY

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This paper forms a part of a systematic investigation on the action of ammonium thiosulphate and ammonia upon chromium and cobalt hydroxides. The action of concentrated ammonia and ammonium thiosulphate upon chromium hydroxide has led to the production of two interesting trinuclear chromium ammonium compounds in which the chromium atoms are linked to one another by single bridges through hydroxyl groups. The preparation, description and the establishment of the constitution of these compounds form the subject of the present paper. Examples of trinuclear cobalt compounds with definite constitution are known. But in the case of chromium, though we are familiar with binuclear compounds like rhodochromium and crythrochromium salts, no trinuclear-ammino-compound of definite constitution has yet been described. Werner (Ber., 1908, 41, 3447) and Weinland and Gussmann (Zeit. anorg. Chem., 1910, 67, 167), however, have described a number of compounds with organic fatty acids which contain three chromium atoms in a molecule. A glance at the formulæ of the compounds, namely, monammino-hexacetato-diol-trichromirhodanat

and hexa-acetato-dihydroxy-triammino-trichromi-iodide

which may be regarded representative of the series, will make it clear. Both the authors have, however, attempted

to clear their constitution, but their views still leave two of the chromium atoms co-ordinatively unsaturated. But these two compounds prepared by the action of ammonium thiosulphate and ammonia upon chromium hydroxide possess the following composition—

Decammin-monaquo-trihydroxy-diol-trichromium thio-sulphate and

Enneaamin-diaquo-trihydroxy-diol-trichromium thiosulphate.

Definite constitution based on Werner's theory can be readily attributed to them; and these have been confirmed by their general behaviour and properties. Their constitutions are represented by the following formulæ:—

and

Both of them are trinuclear compounds with single bridges. The second is evidently formed from the first by the displacement of one molecule of ammonia by a molecule of water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the decammin-monaquo-trihydroxy-diol-trichromium thiosulphate.—Pure chromium hydroxide prepared from 50 grams of chrome alum was mixed with 50 gms. of ammonium thiosulphate dissolved in a small quantity of water; the mixture was then placed in a strong or pressure bottle and saturated with ammonia gas for several hours till a dark violet solution was obtained and the undissolved chromium hydroxide assumed a violet colour. The mixture was then kept in the dark for some days after which it was filtered. The filtrate was then cooled by ice and treated further with a strong current of ammonia gas. After half an hour or so a dark viscous oily liquid separated out at the bottom. The supernatant solution was then decanted into another flask. The oily liquid was first washed several times with a mixture of alcohol and liquor ammonia (1 : 3) to remove any excess of ammonium thiosulphate, then with absolute alcohol when the oil crystallised completely. The crystals were filtered on the pump at once and washed with absolute alcohol and then in some cases with anhydrous ether. They were dried on the pump by strong suction and removed into weighing bottle at once. The crystals could not be dried in a desiccator as the compound would decompose gradually at atmospheric pressure with loss of ammonia; nor was it found possible to dry the crystals in an atmosphere of dry ammonia.

From the mother liquor another crop was obtained by the careful addition of alcohol, an oil separated out which was washed, crystallised and treated as described above. The final mother liquor on exposure to air for a day or two slowly gave a deposit consisting mostly of violet chromium hydroxide mixed with ammonia and a little ammonium thiosulphate. The yield amounted to only 2.2.5 gms.

Properties.—The crystals were reddish violet, very unstable, readily losing ammonia, extremely hygroscopic and turned into oily liquid by the absorption of moisture. With water a dark oil was formed which slowly passed into a violet-coloured solution and decomposed readily with precipitation of chromium hydroxide. It dissolved slowly in strong ammonia to a clear solution and was decomposed readily by caustic alkalies with evolution of ammonia and separation of chromium hydroxide. With dilute acids sulphur dioxide was evolved and sulphur was precipitated. The substance itself was basic to litmus. With moist silver oxide and water the whole of the thiosulphate was removed and the filtrate was strongly basic. Barium chloride solution also removed the whole of the thiosulphate as barium thiosulphate and a violet solution of the corresponding chloride, which was fairly stable, was obtained. This solution was basic to litmus and gave the following reactions.

1. Potassium ferrocyanide solution gave at first a flocculent and then a light blue-violet crystalline precipitate.

2. Potassium ferricyanide solution gave at first a flocculent and then a crystalline pink-coloured precipitate.

3. Mercuric chloride solution gave a light violet-blue flocculent precipitate.

4. Potassium chromate, after the removal of barium by ammonium sulphate, gave no precipitate but potassium dichromate gave a yellowish brown precipitate.

5. Solid potassium iodide gave a light blue gelatinous precipitate.

6. On evaporation with concentrated hydrochloric acid chromic chloride was formed in solution and the characteristic red-violet crystals of chloropentammin chloride separated out.

Results of analysis:—

I. Sample precipitated by alcohol.

0.4832 gm.	gave 0.1277 gm. of Cr_2O_3 ,	Cr=18.11%
" "	" 0.5214 gm. of BaSO_4 ,	S=14.81%
		or S_2O_3 =25.92%
0.3596 "	" 0.0697 gm. of NH_3 ,	NH_3 =19.37%
Hence	Cr : S_2O_3 : NH_3 =3:2 : 10.	

II. Sample precipitated by continuous passage of ammonia,

0.1458 gm.	gave 0.0422 gm. of Cr_2O_3 ,	Cr=19.8%
" "	" 0.1653 gm. of BaSO_4 .	S=15.63%
		or S_2O_3 =27.35%
0.0904 gm.	" 0.0190 gm. of NH_3 ,	NH_3 =21.0%
Hence	Cr: S_2O_3 : NH_3 =3:2:10	

III. Sample precipitated by 30% alcoholic ammonia from the mother liquor of sample II and washed finally with anhydrous ether.

0.2556 gm.	gave 0.0805 gm. of Cr_2O_3 ,	Cr=21.55%
" "	" 0.3500 gm. of BaSO_4 ,	S=18.8%
		or S_2O_3 =32.9%
0.2671 gm.	" 0.06207 " of NH_3 ,	NH_3 =23.24%
Hence	Cr : S_2O_3 : NH_3 =3 : 2 : 10.	

The atomic ratio in all these samples is, therefore, quite constant, the percentage amount only varied due to the change in the extent of hydration.

Constitution.—As the salt decomposed readily in contact with water no conductivity measurement was possible. The action of silver oxide and barium chloride indicated that both the thiosulphate radicles were in the outer zone. The action of concentrated hydrochloric acid indicated the presence of pentammine. In the light of these facts the compound should be represented by the constitutional formula No. (i), page 92.

The action of strong hydrochloric acid can then be represented as follows :—

Preparation of Enneammin-diaquo-trihydroxy-diol-trichromium thiosulphate.—Chromium hydroxide from 50 gms. of chrome alum prepared and purified as described before was mixed with 50 gms. of ammonium thiosulphate dissolved in a small quantity of water; the mixture was placed in a pressure bottle and saturated with ammonia in the cold at 0° C; the bottle was then tightly closed and kept in the dark for 3-4 months. After this time pink-violet crystals separated from the solution and these remained mixed with the undissolved chromium hydroxide. The mass was then agitated with water and the chromium hydroxide removed as suspension by repeated washing. The washing was repeated several times followed by gentle grinding with water. The crystals were afterwards obtained in a fairly pure condition. These were then washed with alcohol and dried in vacuum.

Properties.—It consisted of pink-violet crystals, insoluble in water, slightly alkaline to litmus and quite stable in the dry state. Barium chloride removed the whole of the thiosulphate. Lead acetate and silver nitrate behaved similarly. Concentrated hydrochloric acid gave chloropentammine chloride in small quantities with chromic chloride and an evolution of sulphur dioxide and precipitation of sulphur took place. The solution

obtained by decomposition with barium chloride decomposed slowly in light giving precipitates of chromium hydroxide. A freshly prepared solution obtained by decomposition with barium chloride gave the following reactions:—

1. Potassium ferrocyanide solution gave at first a flocculent then a very light pink crystalline precipitate.
2. Potassium ferricyanide solution gave on warming a dull brown precipitate.
3. Mercuric chloride solution gave a voluminous pink precipitate.
4. Potassium chromate solution, after the removal of barium with ammonium sulphate, gave no precipitate while potassium dichromate gave a light brown crystalline precipitate.
5. Solid potassium iodide gave a heavy pink crystalline precipitate.

Analysis and Composition.

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|-----|--|---------------------------------|
| 1. | 0.1474 gm. of the substance gave 0.0501 gm. of Cr_2O_3 : | Cr=23.2% |
| | " " " " | 0.2057 gm. of BaSO_4 , |
| | | S=19.1% |
| | 0.0570 " " " | 0.0130 gm. of NH_3 , |
| | | $\text{NH}_3=22.75\%$ |
| | 0.0924 " " " | 0.0202 gm. of NH_3 , |
| | | $\text{NH}_3=21.87\%$ |
| II. | 0.2344 gm. of the substance gave 0.0794 gm. of Cr_2O_3 , | Cr=23.00% |
| | " " " " | 0.3163 gm. of BaSO_4 , |
| | | S=18.55% |

$[\text{Cr}_2(\text{NH}_3)_6(\text{OH})_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ requires
 Cr=22.75%, S=18.66%, $\text{NH}_3=22.3\%$ per cent.

Constitution.—The substance was basic to litmus hence it was inferred to be a hydroxo compound. The action of strong hydrochloric acid indicated that it contained a

pentammine group. In its general behaviour with other reagents it resembled the first compound in many respects. Hence its constitution should be represented in a similar way as the first. The constitutional formula No. (ii), page 92 has therefore been adopted.

The action of hydrochloric acid can, therefore, be represented as follows:—

↓
decomposes by heat into
CrCl₃, NH₃ and H₂O.

From the method of formation and the properties of these compounds it appears that in the beginning the first compound is formed in the violet solution obtained by the action of ammonia and ammonium thiosulphate upon the chromium hydroxide. This is precipitated out of the solution by the passage of ammonia or by the addition of alcohol, in the form of an oil. This substance is rather unstable. On the other hand the second compound is quite stable in the dry state and is obtained as well-defined heavy crystals when the violet solution is kept in contact with chromium hydroxide for several months. The first compound is, therefore, gradually changed into the more stable second compound by the conversion of one pentammine residue into an aquotrammine one.

As the compounds are either almost insoluble or unstable in water, their constitution could not be confirmed by physical methods.

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DIAGRAM 1.—MOBIL OIL B.

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

—	at 10 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.
· · · · ·	" 20 " " " " "
— — — — —	" 30 " " " " "
— · — · —	" 40 " " " " "
— · · · —	" 50 " " " " "
— — — — —	" 60 " " " " "